

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17334787

Effect Of Continuous Training On Employee Job Efficiency In CHISCO Transport And GUO Transport, Onitsha Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The study examines the Effect of continuous training on employee job efficiency in Chisco Transport and GUO transport, Onitsha Anambra State. The researcher developed two objectives such as, To analyze the impact of on-the job training on employee job efficiency in Chisco Transport and GUO transport, Onitsha Anambra State. To examine the impact of off-the job training on employee job efficiency in Chisco Transport and GUO transport, Onitsha Anambra State. The research design used for this study is a descriptive study and the cross-sectional survey method was adopted for this study. This enabled the researcher to generate first hand data for the study and for the test of hypotheses. The sources of data for this research were mainly primary data and secondary data. The population of this study comprise the senior staff of the GUO transport firm in Anambra state. The total population for the study is one thousand and eighty-one (1081) staff across While 207 sample size were gotten using Borg & Gall formular. The findings of the study revealed, On-the job training has significant effect on employee job efficiency in Chisco Transport and GUO transport, Onitsha Anambra State. Off-the job training has significant effect on employee job efficiency in Chisco Transport and GUO transport, Onitsha Anambra State. The study concludes that continuous training has significant positive effect on job efficiency in Chisco/GUO transport firm in Nigeria. The study recommends that On-the-job training should be used to reinforce practical skills in real work environments—such as vehicle operation, route planning, safety compliance, and customer interaction—allowing employees to learn while performing their duties under supervision. Off-the-job training should focus on theoretical knowledge, new technologies, regulatory updates, soft skills, and strategic thinking. This can be delivered through workshops, seminars, simulations, and e-learning platforms, ensuring employees gain exposure to new ideas away from operational distractions.

Keywords: continuous training, employee job efficiency, on-the job training, off-the job training, Chisco Transport and GUO transport

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Employees are the most precious asset for any organization in building up or destroying its reputation and profitability (Elnaga & Imran, 2013). Some of the factors that determine the performance of employees are training of employees, organizational policies, working situations, job satisfaction, interactions within the organization (Aktar et al., 2012;). Thus, training is one of the most effective tools to enhance the employee performance and to achieve the organizational objectives and goals effectively and efficiently (Afroz, 2018; Garavan et al., 2020).

In today's fast-evolving business environment, driven by technological progress and changing market trends, the significance of continuous training has become increasingly pronounced (Sundstrom et al., 2016, Nwangwu, Ohanyere, Nwangwu, & Atueyi, 2025). Continuous initiatives serve as pivotal mechanisms for enhancing employee performance and productivity (P&P), positioning employees as invaluable assets within any organization (Kuknor & Kumar, 2024). The necessity to address the knowledge and skills gaps created by evolving work environments compels organizations to prioritize effective training programs that empower their workforce and align with overarching organizational objectives (Hassan, 2022, Ifechukwu-jacobs, & Atueyi, 2024). Continuous training is the most important component of human resource management when it comes to making the best use of human resources as they are an organization's most important asset (Mahapatro, 2022, Ohanyere, Arinze, & Atueyi 2025).

It may occur in a variety of situations, either on- or off-the-job, and inside or outside the organization. Continuous training enhances knowledge and information about a specific field as well as improves opportunities to network (Wang et al. 2021). Continuous training has been reckoned to help employees do their current jobs or help meet current performance requirements, by focusing on specific skills required for the current need. Implementing effective T&D programs is essential for cultivating employee competencies and enhancing organizational productivity. By providing employees with the technical, personal, and professional skills necessary for their roles, organizations foster an environment conducive to individual growth while simultaneously aligning this growth with organizational goals.

Continuous training is the most basic function of human resources management. It is the systematic application of formal processes to help people to acquire the knowledge and skills necessary for them to perform their jobs satisfactorily (Armstrong, 2020, Ifechukwu-Jacobs, Arinze, & Nwangwu, & Atueyi, 2025). These activities have become widespread human resource management practices in organizations worldwide (Hughes et al., 2019). In today's business world, continuous training is the main strategy to perform the institutional objectives. It helps to improve employee and employer performance (Khan et al., 2011; Ruttledge & Cathcart, 2019).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Competition for market access for majority of organizations has recently increased due to changes in the external factors such as globalization, changes in technology, political and economic environments. Therefore, this has seen the need to train and equip employees with certain skills to adapt to the ever evolving market thereby performance is realized. In recent years, there has been tremendous growth of business knowledge and skills within the corporate world. It is worth noting that, the development of human resources has been crucial towards the growth of various industrial skills in addition to the latest technology as well as the factors of production (Awuor, 2013, Onya, Dr Arinze, & Atueyi, 2025).

Each and every organization has the responsibility to develop and implement proper training programs so as to improve the job performance of their employees. It is evident that in order for an organization to achieve sustainability in its goals, it is important for them to optimize the employees' contribution. Therefore, the need for sufficient supply of manpower that is technically competent and has the capability to grow into valuable assets in the organizations is something managers need to implement (Afshan, Sobia, Kamran & Nasir, 2015). Continuous employee training faces several challenges, including budget constraints, time limitations, lack of engagement, difficulty measuring impact, and the need to adapt to new technologies and changing work environments. Additionally, organizations may struggle with training inconsistencies, ineffective training methods, and the resistance of some employees to new training programs.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to examine the effect of continuous training on employee job efficiency in Chisco Transport and GUO transport, Onitsha Anambra State. The followings are the specific objectives.

- i. To analyze the impact of on-the job training on employee job efficiency in Chisco Transport and GUO transport, Onitsha Anambra State.

- ii. To examine the impact of off-the job training on employee job efficiency in Chisco Transport and GUO transport, Onitsha Anambra State.

1.2 Hypotheses

Ho1: On-the job training has no significant effect on employee job efficiency in Chisco Transport and GUO transport, Onitsha Anambra State.

Ho2: Off-the job training has no significant effect on employee job efficiency in Chisco Transport and GUO transport, Onitsha Anambra State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Continuous Training

According to Vidyavihar (2019), continuous training is a process within a short period that uses a systematic and orderly approach, in which non-managerial staff or personnel acquire expertise and skills for specific purposes. Training can be defined as a “systematic process of acquiring knowledge, skills, abilities, and the right attitudes and behaviours to meet job requirements” (Gomez-Mejia, et. al., 2017). According to Abiodun (2010, as cited in Butali & Njoroge, 2017), training is a structured development of expertise, skills, and attitudes required by employees to perform adequately on given tasks.

Training is consists of an organization’s planned efforts to help employees acquire job-related knowledge, skills, abilities, and behaviors, with the goal of applying on the job (Noe & Hollenbeck, 2019). Training is the systematic modification of behavior through learning processes, which enable individuals to upgrade the levels of knowledge, practice, and qualification needed to carry out their tasks efficiently. It improves the performance of both employees and employers (Khan et al., 2011). In addition, according to A. Khan et al. (2016), training helps the workforce adapt flawlessly to new technology thereby increasing the efficiency and productivity of individuals and organizations

Employee training and development are seen as the most important formation of any competent management. Development refers to learning opportunities designed to help employees grow. Such opportunities do not have to be limited to only improving employees’ performance in their current jobs. Development has a long-term focus to help the employees to prepare for future work demands while training focuses on the immediate period to help fix any current deficits in employees’ skills (Bernadin & Russell, 2013).

As a result, training involves making plans to prepare various learning strategies for the staff in an effort to improve their capacity to accomplish the desired result (Burhan et al., 2021). Development, in contrast to training, which takes place right now and covers every single staff member's responsibilities, attempts to comprehend the mechanisms of things and future difficulties rather than just existing processes generally (Anwar & Ghafoor, 2017). It also occurs over a longer period of time.

2.1.2 On-the-Job Training

On-the-Job Training (OTJ) is a technique of providing training to employees while they are at work in their working environment. The goal of this training is to familiarize the employees with typical working conditions, which means that, during the training period, the workers will be directly involved in using machinery, equipment, devices, materials, and so on (Enga, 2017). In addition, it also aids the employees in determining how to deal with problems that may arise over the course of their work. The most important aspect of this training is learning by doing, in which a supervisor or experienced staff demonstrates to the trainees how to complete specific tasks. Newbies or unskilled employees learn through observing fellow employees or managers doing their jobs and attempting to imitate their activities.

These approaches are less expensive and less disruptive because the employees are always on the job, training is delivered on the same machines, experiences are based on the established standards, and the trainees are learning while earning (Raheja, 2015). According to Armstrong (1995), on-the-job training entails teaching trainees lessons by skilled and experienced staff members that are relevant to the job and

do not deviate from the nature of the job, as well as organizing it in other ways by creating seminars or an efficient distribution between staff members to teach one another collectively (Anwar & Abdullah, 2021).

2.1.3 Off-the-Job Training

On the other hand, Off-the-Job Training is a training method in which workers or employees learn their job roles away from their actual working environment. Simply said, off-the-job training is an area set apart for training that is specialized in a single workplace, where employees are required to discover their abilities and become well-equipped with equipment and techniques that will be employed on that specific work floor. According to Raheja (2015), off-the-job training methods are used to take place outside the workplace, study materials are provided, entire attention is placed on learning rather than performing, and there is freedom of speech. Lectures and conferences, vestibule training, and sensitivity training are all important means of off-the-job training.

2.1.4 Employee Job Efficiency

Employee job efficiency refers to how effectively and productively employees utilize their time and resources to achieve their work goals and contribute to organizational objectives. It involves maximizing output while minimizing wasted effort and resources Employee Efficiency Workplace efficiency is critical. Additionally, companies must cost-effectively develop their goods to be successful (Everard & Burrow, 2011). As Schermerhorn, Davidson, Factor, Poole, and Woods (2017) note, Drucker's famous comment. "There is probably nothing so worthless as doing with great efficiency what should not be done at all" provides a way of distinguishing between effectiveness and efficiency. It's only efficient if it's useful.

To put it another way, efficient action produces a beneficial outcome. It must be able to do its job (Noordzij, 2013). When efficiency is already in existence, it is possible to speak about efficiency. To be efficient, one must be able to accomplish a task or generate a product by using as little resources, time, or effort as possible. When it comes to reaching organizational objectives, it's all about resources and speed. The maxim "doing things well" was coined by Drucker in 1974. When it comes to determining how efficient a company is, production is the metric that matters most (Everard & Burrow, 2001).

2.2 Theoretical Review

The Human Capital Theory

According to Manning, (2015) organizations that take their employees through training are considered to have made an investment in human resources (HR). Through training assets such as knowledge and skills are created. These assets then in turn increase the productivity of the employee. Schultz argues that the skilled human resource is able to acquire such through training programs or reinventing the current programs through well factored on-the job training programs in an organization. Jayakumar et al., (2014) proposes that under human capital theory people's varied attributes form the organization capital and investment in such earns the organization returns that return.

In this theory, employers need to invest in specific training programs and create more promotion opportunities to enhance employees' career path prospects. Sung and Choi, (2014) proved that managerial training is relatively effective when he postulated his meta-analysis theory of managerial training effects. He was of the idea that the sole aim of training in any organization was to bolster the employees' capabilities and organizational performance. He further stated that, through investing in training of its employees, an organization realizes more productive and effective employees which is an investment to them hence an asset too.

Empirical Webometrics-Continuous Training and Employee Job Efficiency

S N	Author (s)	TOPIC	Variables	Major findings
	Kamanda and Iravo, (2017)	examined effects of staff training on efficient stores operations in Kenya tea development authority	staff training on efficient stores operations	According to the analysis of findings, the respondent indicated that KTDA factories do not offer regular training to stores personnel on store management and this has affected store operations negatively
	Ibienieye, Amah, and Okocha, (2022)	evaluated theoretically the relationship between training and employees' efficiency in Universities in Rivers State.	training and employees' efficiency	The literature reviewed showed a significant effect of training on employee efficiency.
	Nur, et al. (2022)	determined the impact of training and development on organizational performance in order to figure out how the training and development (on-the-job training, off-the-job training, job rotation) can impact organizational performance	training and development on organizational performance	The findings indicate that all three hypotheses are accepted
	Mohammad and Hamdullah, (2025) ity	explored the critical impact of Training and Development (T&D) on improving employees' Performance and Productivity	entrepreneurial education's on graduate venture creation	the findings, which reveal a strong and statistically significant positive relationship between T&D initiatives and enhancements in employee performance and productivity (P&P) at JACK NGO. Notably, on-the-job training is a particularly effective facet of T&D, directly contributing to enhanced employee outcomes.
	Mohammed, (2022)	investigated the impact of training on employees' performance in the technology focused academic institution	entrepreneurial culture and venture creation	Results show that training design, training needs assessment, training delivery style and training evaluation have significant positive effect on employees' performance.
	Mabeya and Rotich, (2016)	examined the influence of training	training on performance of	The study found out that training is given adequate importance at

	on performance of employees in Kenya, a case study of Kenya national youth service	employees	NYS, skills learnt in training are helpful to the workers, training is periodically evaluated, the senior staff inducts junior employees on use of tools and equipment, and tools and equipment are provided to all employees.
Kasingu, (2018)	examined the effects of training on employee performance in manufacturing sector at Eagle Vet Kenya Limited (EVK).	training on employee performance	The study found out that on the job training affect the performance of employees within the manufacturing industry as this is shown by the 60% of the respondents who strongly supported.
Falola (2014)	set out to explore the impact of training and development on the performance of workers and the competitiveness of organizations in Nigeria's banking sector	training and development the performance	The design of a training program has the greatest influence on post-training job performance, coupled with trainees' self-efficacy and post-training behavior.
Diamantidis, and Chatzoglou (2014)	investigated the medium- to long-term effects on firms of training programs	training programs and performance	The study found that entrepreneurship education had no connection with entrepreneurial orientation or business performance.

METHODOLOGY

3.1: Research Design

Survey research design was used in carrying out the study. Ikeagwu (1997) opined that studies of this nature will be survey method to look for information on facts, attitudes, practices and opinions of the respondents.

3.2: Sources of Data

The source of data collection for this research work was derived from two specific areas, the primary and the secondary sources. In this study, the data collection technique was based on questionnaire. The researcher developed the questionnaire that will be administered to the respondents.

3.3 Population of the Study

The population of this study comprise the senior staff of the GUO transport firm in Anambra state. The total population for the study is one thousand and eighty-one (1081) staff across

3.4 Sample size determinants

Given the nature of this study, it was difficult to cover the entire population of (1081), so a fair representative sample of the population therefore was imperative. Accordingly, the sample size for the study was determined by using the Borg & Gall (1973) formular for calculating sample size as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 n &= (1.960)^2 (0.05) [1081] \\
 n &= (1.960)^2 (0.05) [1081] \\
 n &= (3.8461) (54.05) \\
 &= 207.881 \quad \Rightarrow \quad 207 \\
 n &= 207
 \end{aligned}$$

The research adopts two sampling techniques, namely purposive sampling and stratified sampling. Purposive sampling enables the researcher to choose the respondents that were of interest to the study while the stratified random sampling permits each of the different respondents in all the different states to be selected without bias.

3.5: Method of Data Collection.

The major research instrument adopted for the study is the uses of structured questionnaire to elicit responses for the sample population. This instrument of the collection is divided into two.

SECTION A: Deals in the bio-data of the respondent while section,

B: Deals in the question while respondents are expected to respond to, depending on their choice.

3.6 Method of Data Analysis.

In this study, the descriptive statistics such frequency counts with simple percentage were used to analyse bio-data of the respondents and the four research questions. At the inferential level of analysis, linear regression were used to test hypotheses 1, 2, 3, and 4 to determine the extent of correlation between x and y variables (Independent and Dependent). All analyses were done through the application of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS 20 windows).

PRESENTATION ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Two hundred and seven (207) copies of questionnaire were administered among the selected respondents. However, one hundred and seventy-two (172) copies of questionnaire were retrieved. Therefore, the analysis and interpretation of data were only based on the returned questionnaire. The validity and reliability of this study is highly ensured, despite the number of questionnaires not returned. The method used was percentage table technique and t-test for the hypothesis. The method was adopted because it possesses a unique estimating property which includes unbiased, efficiency and consistency when compared with other linear unbiased estimates.

4.1 Demographic Table

4.1.1 SEX

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	MALE	104	31.0	60.5	60.5
	FEMALE	68	20.3	39.5	100.0
	Total	172	51.3	100.0	

Sources: SPSS Output 2025

The above table reveals that the one hundred and four of the respondents which represents fifty-seven (60.5) persons were male respondents, while sixty-eight (68) respondents which represent 39.5% were female respondents. By implication, male respondents were more than female respondents by 21.0% in our selected population sample for this study. The implication of this is to enable us to know the number of female and male that successfully returned their questionnaire.

4.1.2 Status

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
MARRIED	82	24.5	47.7	47.7
SINGLE	58	17.3	33.7	81.4
Valid DIVORCED	15	4.5	8.7	90.1
SEPERATED	17	5.1	9.9	100.0
Total	172	51.3	100.0	

Sources: SPSS Output 2025

In the table above, out of the one hundred and seventy-two (172) respondents, eighty-two (82) of the respondents were married. While fifty-eight (58) respondents which represent 33.7 percent are single. Fifteen (15) respondents which represent 8.7 were divorced, while separated were seventeen (17), which represent 9.9. Thus marital status table help us to know the number of single, married, and divorce respondents that answered the distributed questionnaire.

4.1.3 Education qualification

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
WAEC/NECO	52	15.5	30.2	30.2
B.SC/HND	93	27.8	54.1	84.3
Valid MSC	20	6.0	11.6	95.9
PHD	7	2.1	4.1	100.0
Total	172	51.3	100.0	

Sources: SPSS Output 2025

The table above indicates that fifty-two (52) respondents which representing 30.2% maintain to acquired WAEC/NECO, while 54.1% percent of the respondents which represents ninety-three (93) is B.sc/HND. Twenty (20) which represent 11.6 percept have m.sc, while seven (7) have P.hd. This as the one of demographic item helps us to identify the education qualification of the respondent

4.1.4 Age

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
18-25	20	6.0	11.6	11.6
26-33	42	12.5	24.4	36.0
Valid 34-40	47	14.0	27.3	63.4
41-50	20	6.0	11.6	75.0
51-BOVE	43	12.8	25.0	100.0
Total	172	51.3	100.0	

Sources: SPSS Output 2025

The above table reveals that the 11.6% of the respondents which represents twenty (20) persons were within the age bracket 18-25, while forty-two (42) respondents which represent 24.4% were within the age bracket 26-33. Again, 27.3% of the respondents which represents forty-seven (47) persons were within the age bracket 34-40, while twenty (20) respondents which represent 11.6% were within the age bracket 41-50. Lastly, forty-three (43) respondents which represent 25.0% were within the age bracket 51 and above. The implication of this is to enable us to know the age bracket of respondents that successfully returned their questionnaire.

4.2 Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis one

Ho1: On-the job training has no significant effect on employee job efficiency in Chisco Transport and GUO transport, Onitsha Anambra State.

ANOVA

Table 4.2.1

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	139.809	4	34.952	47.346	.000
Within Groups	90.065	172	.738		
Total	229.874	172			

Sources: SPSS Output 2025

In testing this hypothesis, the F-statistics and probability value in table 4.7 is used. On-the job training variables have a F-statistics of 47.346 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that On-the job training has significant effect on employee job efficiency in Chisco Transport and GUO transport, Onitsha Anambra State

Hypothesis Two

Ho2: Off-the job training has no significant effect on employee job efficiency in Chisco Transport and GUO transport, Onitsha Anambra State.

ANOVA

Table 4.2.2

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	182.143	2	45.536	40.358	.000
Within Groups	137.652	172	1.128		
Total	319.795	172			

Sources: SPSS Output 2025

Second hypothesis has f-statistics of 40.358 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses and conclude that Off-the job training has significant effect on employee job efficiency in Chisco Transport and GUO transport, Onitsha Anambra State

4.3 Discussion of The Findings

On-the job training and employee job efficiency

Job training plays a critical role in enhancing employee job efficiency within transport firms in Nigeria. The dynamic nature of the transport sector—marked by technological advancement, safety requirements, and customer service expectations—demands a workforce that is not only skilled but also adaptable. This study confirms that well-structured training programs improve employees' technical capabilities, reduce operational errors, and foster a more productive work environment. Furthermore, ongoing training

initiatives contribute to higher job satisfaction and employee retention, which are essential for long-term organizational success. Therefore, transport firms in Nigeria must invest consistently in relevant, practical, and continuous training programs to ensure optimal performance and competitiveness in the industry. The study is in line with the study of Afroz, (2018). Afshan, Sobia, Kamran, & Nasir, (2012). Aktar, Sachu, & Ali., (2012) who found a positive significant relation between On-the job training and employee job efficiency

Off-the job training and employee job efficiency

Off-the-job training has proven to be a valuable tool in improving employee job efficiency in transport firms across Nigeria. By allowing employees to acquire new skills and knowledge in a structured environment away from daily operational pressures, this form of training enhances learning outcomes and encourages innovation. The findings suggest that employees who undergo off-the-job training demonstrate greater competence, adaptability, and confidence in performing their duties. Moreover, such training contributes to a safer and more efficient transport operation, especially in areas like logistics management, vehicle handling, and customer service. To remain competitive and responsive to industry demands, Nigerian transport firms should prioritize regular off-the-job training programs as part of their strategic human resource development. The study is in line with the study of Burhan et al. (2021), Butali, & Njoroge, (2017). Elnaga, & Imran, (2013). who found a positive significant relation between Off-the job training and employee job efficiency

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Summary of findings

The following were the major findings of the study:

1. On-the job training has significant effect on employee job efficiency in Chisco Transport and GUO transport, Onitsha Anambra State
2. Off-the job training has significant effect on employee job efficiency in Chisco Transport and GUO transport, Onitsha Anambra State

5.2 Conclusions

Continuous training is essential for sustaining and enhancing employee job efficiency in transport firms in Nigeria. Given the evolving nature of the transport industry—driven by technological advancements, regulatory changes, and increasing customer expectations—employees must continuously update their skills and knowledge to remain effective. This study highlights that continuous training leads to improved job performance, better problem-solving abilities, and increased compliance with safety and operational standards. It also fosters employee motivation and reduces errors, delays, and accidents, all of which are crucial in transport operations. Therefore, Nigerian transport firms should institutionalize continuous training as a core component of their workforce development strategy to ensure operational excellence and long-term competitiveness.

5.3 Recommendations

1. On-the-job training should be used to reinforce practical skills in real work environments—such as vehicle operation, route planning, safety compliance, and customer interaction—allowing employees to learn while performing their duties under supervision.
2. Off-the-job training should focus on theoretical knowledge, new technologies, regulatory updates, soft skills, and strategic thinking. This can be delivered through workshops, seminars, simulations, and e-learning platforms, ensuring employees gain exposure to new ideas away from operational distractions.

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